

Studies on Complexes of Copper(II) and Nickel(II) with Alkyl Xanthates and Their Mixed Chelates with Oxine and 2-Picolinic Acid

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Simple complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with xanthates of isomeric alcohols of the composition ML_2 have been prepared, where L=isopropyl or isobutyl or isoamyl xanthate. These simple complexes on reacting with hetero donor ligands (X), like oxine and 2-picolinic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio form mixed ligand complexes having general formula MLX . All these complexes have been characterised on the basis of chemical analyses, molar conductance, magnetic moment, and infrared and electronic spectral data. The magnetic and electronic spectral studies provide evidence for the existence of square planar structure for CuL_2 , CuLX and NiL_2 , and tetrahedral structure for NiLX .

SIMPLE and mixed metal xanthates are quite important as insecticides and fungicides¹ and they have found use in analytical separations, in vulcanisation of rubber², as antioxidants³ and as lubricants⁴. A survey of literature reveals that some metal complexes involving only simple alkyl xanthates are reported. In view of the importance of this type of complex compounds it was, therefore, thought worthwhile to prepare complexes of some higher isomeric alkyl xanthates. The present study reports the preparation of copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes with isopropyl, isobutyl and isoamyl xanthates. Further, some mixed chelates using oxine and 2-picolinic acid have also been prepared.

Experimental

Potassium isopropyl, isobutyl and isoamyl xanthates were prepared and purified as reported in the literature⁵. Bis-isopropyl, isobutyl and isoamyl xanthates of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} were prepared following the method reported earlier⁶.

Reaction of bis-xanthato Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with oxine or 2-picolinic acid: To a chloroform suspension of Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} xanthato complexes, a chloroform solution of oxine or 2-picolinic acid was added in 1:1 molar ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for 2 h and the separated compound was suction-filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Cu, Ni, C, N and S were estimated by standard methods. Infrared spectra in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} were recorded at C.D.R.I., Lucknow. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on solid specimens using Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. The electronic spectra in CHCl_3 or

acetone solution were recorded using Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The molar conductance was measured in $\sim 10^{-3} M$ solution using Toshniwal CLO 102 conductivity bridge and a dip type cell.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1. Infrared and electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

As expected, all the compounds are found to be non-electrolytes and have very low molar conductance values. Magnetic moment measurements throw some light on the stereochemistry of these complexes. The μ_{eff} values of Cu^{II} simple and mixed chelates lie in the range 1.80-1.84 B.M. which is indicative of the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for a $3d^9$ cupric ion. It was reported earlier that magnetic moment values for tetrahedral Cu^{II} complexes are always higher (≥ 2.0 B.M.) than the values for square planar complexes which lie nearer the spin-only value of ~ 1.80 B.M. Thus, the observed values suggest that all the copper complexes are square planar involving $3d_4s_4p^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

Simple Ni^{II} xanthates are essentially diamagnetic in nature indicating a square planar configuration. On the other hand, Ni^{II} mixed chelate complexes (NiLX) have magnetic moments in the range 3.12-3.22 B.M., indicating the presence of two unpaired electrons as expected for a tetrahedral configuration for Ni^{II} utilising $4s_4p^2$ hybrid orbitals for bonding.

The molecular weight measurements carried out by Rast's camphor method indicate that all the complexes are monomeric in nature.

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TABLE 1—ELEMENTAL ANALYSES, MELTING POINT AND MAGNETIC SUSCEPTIBILITY DATA FOR Cu^{II} AND Ni^{II} SIMPLE AND MIXED CHLORATES

Sl. no.	Complex*	M.p. (°C)	μ_{eff} B.M.	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
				M	C	N	S
1.	Cu(IPX) ₂	172	1.80	19.16 (19.02)	28.56 (28.76)	—	38.24 (38.35)
2.	Cu(IBX) ₂	165 d	1.82	17.35 (17.55)	33.02 (33.17)	—	32.75 (32.83)
3.	Cu(IAX) ₂	159	1.82	16.45 (16.29)	37.12 (36.94)	—	32.75 (32.83)
4.	Ni(IPX) ₂	127	Diamag.	17.63 (17.85)	28.95 (29.19)	—	39.20 (38.91)
5.	Ni(IBX) ₂	140	Diamag.	16.28 (16.45)	33.56 (33.62)	—	—
6.	Ni(IAX) ₂	99	Diamag.	15.32 (15.25)	37.62 (37.40)	—	—
7.	Cu(IPX)(OX)	250	1.82	18.56 (18.49)	45.72 (45.43)	4.15 (4.07)	18.78 (18.64)
8.	Cu(IBX)(OX)	180	1.84	17.86 (17.75)	—	4.02 (3.91)	18.12 (17.89)
9.	Cu(IAX)(OX)	189	1.83	17.24 (17.03)	48.26 (48.43)	—	—
10.	Cu(IPX)(Pyca)	176 d	1.84	20.02 (19.08)	37.64 (37.42)	4.45 (4.36)	20.45 (19.96)
11.	Cu(IBX)(Pyca)	208 d	1.82	18.66 (18.97)	—	4.26 (4.18)	19.26 (19.12)
12.	Cu(IAX)(Pyca)	205 d	1.83	18.42 (18.21)	41.18 (41.30)	3.92 (4.01)	—
13.	Ni(IPX)(OX)	250	3.20	17.14 (17.32)	46.25 (46.04)	4.26 (4.13)	18.64 (18.89)
14.	Ni(IBX)(OX)	182 d	3.14	16.82 (16.63)	47.24 (47.61)	—	18.26 (18.14)
15.	Ni(IAX)(OX)	250	3.22	16.22 (16.00)	49.28 (49.06)	3.92 (3.81)	—
16.	Ni(IPX)(Pyca)	250	3.12	18.26 (18.58)	37.82 (38.00)	—	20.15 (20.26)
17.	Ni(IBX)(Pyca)	250	3.20	17.05 (17.80)	39.85 (40.02)	4.46 (4.24)	19.62 (19.40)
18.	Ni(IAX)(Pyca)	250	3.22	17.02 (16.83)	42.04 (41.88)	4.16 (4.07)	—

* IPX = Isopropyl xanthate, IBX = isobutyl xanthate, IAX = isoamyl xanthate, OX = oxine, Pyca = 2-picolinic acid.

Infrared spectra : Alkyl xanthates are uninegative bidentate ligands and are bound to the metal ion through both its sulphur atoms. The structure of metal(II) xanthates can be represented as resonance hybrid of the three canonical forms, (A), (B) and (C).

Chatt *et al.*⁷ have suggested that the resonance form (C) is of minor importance primarily because the infrared spectrum does not exhibit the $\nu_{C=O}$ band but a ν_{C-O} at $\sim 1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The resonance from (A) or (B) describes the most probable structure of metal(II) xanthates.

In the infrared spectrum of PIPX, PIBX and PIAX (free ligands), the ν_{C-O} band appeared in the range $1044-1135$ and $1130-1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$, whereas in simple xanthates and mixed xanthato complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II}, the ν_{C-O} bands were observed in the range $1088-1170$ and $1142-1200\text{ cm}^{-1}$, respectively. These observations were in accord with the findings of Little *et al.*⁸.

In the free potassium alkyl xanthates, the $\nu_{C=S}$ appeared in the range $1040-1090\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and in complexes the band is shifted to a lower frequency and lies in the range $1005-1060\text{ cm}^{-1}$. This lowering of the $\nu_{C=S}$ band indicated the involvement of sulphur in bonding with the metals⁹.

In oxine complexes many bands due to oxine are found to be overlapping with the bands of xanthates. However, an additional characteristic band for $\nu_{C=O}$ was observed at $\sim 1110\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which indicates the

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹) OF SIMPLE AND MIXED CHELATES OF Cu^{II} AND Ni^{II}

Sl. no.	Complex*	$\nu_{\text{asy C-S}}$	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-N}}$	$\nu_{\text{M-S}}$	λ_{max}
1.	Cu(IPX) ₂	1015	1090 1142	—	405	15385
2.	Cu(IBX) ₂	1035	1170 1200	—	400	15625
3.	Cu(IAX) ₂	1040	1155 1200	—	395	15625
4.	Ni(IPX) ₂	1021	1089 1152	—	397	20000, 23255
5.	Ni(IBX) ₂	1045	1160 1182	—	400	20000, 23255
6.	Ni(IAX) ₂	1040	1150 1170	—	390	20000, 23255
7.	Cu(IPX)(OX)	1028	1088 1158	325	410	15156
8.	Cu(IPX)(OX)	1038	1178 1200	335	410	14777
9.	Cu(IAX)(OX)	1035	1142 1195	330	395	15156
10.	Cu(IPX)(Pyca)	1008	1090 1150	338	395	14777
11.	Cu(IBX)(Pyca)	1038	1168 1190	338	390	14705
12.	Cu(IAX)(Pyca)	1035	1140 1192	335	410	14777
13.	Ni(IPX)(OX)	1032	1098 1142	310	410	11765, 15150
14.	Ni(IBX)(OX)	1042	1155 1175	300	390	11765, 15150
15.	Ni(IBX)(OX)	1035	1145 1178	300	410	11628, 15150
16.	Ni(IPX)(Pyca)	1022	1090 1150	295	385	11494, 14925
17.	Ni(IBX)(Pyca)	1025	1150 1170	300	390	11494, 15150
18.	Ni(IAX)(Pyca)	1025	1150 1170	310	385	11494, 15384

* Abbreviations as in Table 1.

presence of oxine group in the mixed chelate complexes as observed by earlier workers⁹. Further, the presence of additional bands due to picolinic acid in the mixed chelate complexes indicated its definite presence¹⁰.

The metal-sulphur (M-S) bands for simple and mixed chelates of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} appearing in the range 390-410 cm⁻¹ (Table 2) confirmed the bonding of xanthate through sulphur atoms^{11,12}. The metal-nitrogen (M-N) band for mixed complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} appeared in the range 295-338 cm⁻¹ which gave direct evidence for the presence of oxine and picolinic acid bonded through nitrogen to the metal ion.

Electronic spectra: The electronic spectra of simple and mixed chelates of Cu^{II} show a broad band in the region 14500-16000 cm⁻¹ which indicate square planar configuration for all the Cu^{II} complexes¹³⁻¹⁵. The simple chelates of Ni^{II} xanthates exhibit two medium bands or shoulders at ~20000 and ~23255 cm⁻¹ indicating square planar environment around Ni^{II} with D_{4h} symmetry as observed by earlier workers^{16,17}. For mixed chelate complexes of Ni^{II}, however, the bands were observed at ~15100 and ~11600 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to a tetrahedral environment around Ni^{II} as observed¹⁸ earlier.

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